

Coordination complexes of Transitional Metals with 1-Phenyl-3- α -Pyridyltriazene.

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Complexes like Cu(PPT)py , Cu(PPT) , Cu(PPT)_2 , Ni(PPT)_2 , Co(PPT)_2 and Pd(PPT)X ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}$, Br , I), have been prepared with 1-phenyl-3- α -pyridyltriazene (PPTH) and their structural investigations made on the basis of magnetic, spectral and X-ray powder diffraction studies. The diamagnetic complexes, Cu(PPT)py and Pd(PPT)X , are suggested to have identical bridged polymeric structure. Subnormal magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) of 0.89 B.M. for Cu(PPT)_2 indicates antiferromagnetic interactions. Magnetic and spectral studies of Ni(PPT)_2 and Co(PPT)_2 show them to be octahedral, in which class also falls Cu(PPT)_2 , as the three complexes are found to be isomorphous. Bridged octahedral structures are proposed for them.

In a previous communication¹, we have reported the synthesis of some complexes of copper (II), nickel(II), cobalt (II) and cobalt (III) with bidentate para-substituted diphenyltriazene and discussed their probable structures. Some of them are found to be either bridged dimeric or polymeric and others monomeric possibly forming 4-membered rings. In order to investigate the effect of introducing another coordination centre in the 1, 3-diphenyltriazene so that atridentate ligand capable of making two interlocked 4-membered rings might be formed, 1-phenyl-3- α -pyridyltriazene, $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4$ (PPTH) (Fig. 1), has been prepared. In the present work, a number of complexes of copper(I), copper(II), nickel(II),

Fig. 1.

cobalt (II) and palladium (II) with this new ligand have been prepared and characterised them on the basis of magnetic, spectral and X-ray powder diffraction studies.

Experimental

Ligand: 1-Phenyl-3- α -pyridyltriazene (PPTH). The ligand, prepared according to the method of Chichibabin², is obtained as yellowish-white needles (m. p. = 176°). It can be preserved at room temperature for indefinite period and is highly soluble in benzene and pyridine, moderately soluble in ethanol, chloroform and carbontetrachloride.

Complexes: Pyridine-(1-phenyl-3- α -pyridyltriazene)-copper (I), Cu(PPT)py . 0.95g of freshly prepared cuprous iodide (0.005 mole) dissolved in 7 ml of

hot pyridine was added immediately to 100 ml of an alcoholic solution of 1 g of triazene (0.005 mole) with vigorous stirring. The light-yellow crystalline precipitate formed turned orange on the addition of 5 ml of an ethanolic solution of 1(N) caustic soda. The precipitate was filtered at once, washed with water and ethanol and rapidly crystallised from pyridine as reddish-yellow needles.

The complex is insoluble in water, slightly soluble in ethanol, moderately in chloroform, carbontetrachloride, benzene, acetone and dioxan, and highly soluble in pyridine.

1-Phenyl-3- α -pyridyltriazene-copper (I), Cu(PPT) . The complex was prepared from the pyridino-complex, Cu(PPT)py . The pyridine was removed completely at 130°C, the residue left was crystallised from benzene when shining reddish orange crystals were obtained.

The compound is slightly soluble in ethyl alcohol, carbontetrachloride, acetone, benzene and chloroform.

Bis (1-phenyl-3- α -pyridyltriazene)-copper(II), Cu(PPT)_2 . To a hot solution of 0.8 g of ligand (0.004 mole) in 80 ml of ethanol was added slowly with stirring 10 ml of an ethanolic solution of 0.34 g of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.002 mole). A green precipitate was immediately formed which settled down on adding 4 ml of an ethanolic solution of (N) caustic soda. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water, ethanol and dried in air.

The complex is slightly soluble in ethyl alcohol, chloroform, carbontetrachloride, benzene, pyridine, dioxan and acetone.

Bis (1-phenyl-3- α -pyridyltriazene)-nickel (II) and bis (1-phenyl-3- α -pyridyltriazene)-cobalt(II), Ni(PPT)_2 and Co(PPT)_2 . These complexes were obtained as yellow or brown micro crystals on mixing 20 ml of an ethanolic solution of 0.5 g of $\text{MCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{M}=\text{Ni}$ or Co) (0.002 mole) with 80 ml of an ethanolic solution of 0.8 g of ligand (0.004 mole) followed by the addition of 4 ml

of an ethanolic solution of (*N*) caustic soda, when the compound settled down. It was filtered, washed with water and dried in air.

The compounds are insoluble in water, sufficiently soluble in pyridine, moderately soluble in benzene but slightly soluble in chloroform, carbontetrachloride, acetone, ethyl alcohol and dioxan.

Halogen-(1-phenyl-3- α -pyridyltriazeno)-palladium (II), Pd(PPT)X, (X=Cl, Br or I). 0.18-0.36 g of PdX₂ (0.001 mole) was dissolved in 50 ml of acetone in presence of a little quantity of KX and added to 20 ml of a solution of 0.2 g of the triazene (0.001 mole) in acetone when a precipitate was formed. The compound, after filtration, was washed with acetone and water and air-dried.

The compounds are slightly soluble in ethyl alcohol, benzene, carbontetrachloride, chloroform, acetone and pyridine.

Measurements of magnetic susceptibility: Magnetic measurements were made in a Gouy balance at room temperature with mercury tetrathiocyanato cobaltate as standard.

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra of the complexes in solution using benzene as solvent were measured in Hilger Uvispek and Spectromom-201 Spectrophotometers. The reflectance spectra in solid were also obtained in the Hilger Spectrophotometer with a reflectance attachment using MgCO₃ as standard.

Infra-red spectra: The infra-red spectra of copper (II), nickel (II) and cobalt (II) complexes in KBr discs were recorded in Perkin-Elmer IR 237B spectrophotometer.

The far-infrared spectra in Nujol were measured in a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer.

X-ray diffraction: These were taken using Guinier Camera with CuK _{α} radiation.

Results and Discussion

The complexes isolated together with their properties and analytical data are collected in Table I. The

reddish-orange diamagnetic copper (I) complex, Cu(PPT)py, prepared in presence of pyridine, contains one mole of ligand and one mole of pyridine whereas the corresponding 1, 3-diphenyl-triazeno-copper (I) complex contains one mole of the ligand and two moles of pyridine³, both being prepared under identical conditions. Cu(PPT)py loses the pyridine molecule completely at 130° and thereby is converted to a yellow product conforming to the composition Cu(PPT) with $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 0.0$ B.M. This residue again on crystallisation from benzene yields a reddish-orange crystalline diamagnetic complex of the same composition.

The pyridino-cuprous complex, Cu(PPT)py, on long standing in the air or in pyridine medium changes into a green copper (II) complex, Cu(PPT)₂. Molecular model⁴ shows that for copper (I) a monomeric structure (Fig. 2) with two interlocked 4-membered rings would

Fig. 2.

become highly strained, so also a dimeric structure (Fig. 3). On the other hand, no strain is indicated in a polymeric structure (Fig. 4) where the triazene first acts as a bidentate ligand forming a 6-membered chelate with one metal ion and then the imino hydrogen of the ligand is replaced by another metal ion to form a bridge. The organic molecule, thus, acts as a tridentate

TABLE I—PROPERTIES AND ANALYTICAL DATA ON METAL-COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour and nature of crystals.	Decomp. point (°C)	%Metal		%Nitrogen		%Halogen	
			Fd.	Cald.	Fd.	Cald.	Fd.	Cald.
Cu(PPT)py	Reddish orange needles	—	18.90	18.71	20.45	20.62	—	—
Cu(PPT)	Reddish orange micro crystals	275	24.25	24.38	21.46	21.50	—	—
Cu(PPT) ₂	Deep green micro crystals	232	13.90	13.88	24.38	24.47	—	—
Ni(PPT) ₂	Deep yellow micro crystals	290	12.85	12.96	24.82	24.74	—	—
Co(PPT) ₂	Brown micro crystals	270	12.82	13.01	24.85	24.73	—	—
Pd(PPT)Cl	Bright yellow needles	190	31.35	31.45	16.50	16.50	10.54	10.60
Pd(PPT)Br	Orange yellow needles	180	27.76	27.81	14.75	14.60	20.74	20.83
Pd(PPT)I	Orange needles	176	24.73	24.82	13.22	13.00	29.52	29.46

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC AND SPECTRAL DATA OF METAL-COMPLEXES

Complex	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Molar Conc. in benzene	Absorption max.		Molar absorbance E_{max}
			nm	(λ_{max}) Cm^{-1}	
Cu(PPT)py	Diamagnetic	2×10^{-5}	400	25,000	11,480
Cu(PPT)	"	2×10^{-5}	395	25,300	10,590
Cu(PPT) ₂	0.89	2×10^{-5}	380	26,300	33,440
		Solid	620	16,130	—
			685	14,600	—
Ni(PPT) ₂	3.26	2×10^{-5}	390	25,600	19,000
		7.7×10^{-8}	670	14,920	14.2
			1080	9,260	10.6
Co(PPT) ₂	5.37	2×10^{-5}	395	25,300	13,840
		15×10^{-8}	1060	9,430	5.4
Pd(PPT)Cl	Diamagnetic	2×10^{-5}	425	23,500	9,200
Pd(PPT)Br	"	2×10^{-5}	405	24,700	10,500
Pd(PPT)I	"	2×10^{-5}	380	26,300	9,920

Fig. 3.

Fig. 4.

Fig. 5.

ligand; the fourth coordination position being occupied by the pyridine molecule. The trivalent copper (I) complex, Cu (PPT), may not have either a monomeric or dimeric structure but a polymeric structure like Fig. 4 is possible without the pyridine molecule.

The copper (II) compound, Cu (PPT)₂, exhibits anomalous magnetic behaviour with a subnormal magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) of 0.89 B.M. at room temperature (Table 2). The low magnetic moment may be due to the antiferromagnetic interactions between copper (II) ions present probably in a polymeric molecule. From pyridine the complex can be crystallised unchanged showing the metal to be coordinately saturated with two tridentate ligands leaving no accommodation for excess pyridine. Molecular model shows that a structure similar to that of bridged dimeric planar [Cu(DPT)₂]₂⁵ is not likely if the bidentate diphenyltriazenide anion DPT⁻ is replaced by a tridentate anion PPT⁻ and the pyridino nitrogen of the ligand is also

made to coordinate and simultaneously bridge the two copper (II) ions making two octahedra. An alternative polymeric distorted octahedral arrangement of the highly stable complex, relieved from such a strain, is proposed (Fig. 5) based on the model of Cu (PPT) py complex (Fig. 4), in which the two axial bonds are shown to be elongated than the four equatorial bonds which is definitely possible with a d^9 system (Cu^{2+}).

In such a structure, any two copper (II) ions cannot form direct exchange interaction because of the presence of intervening bridging systems. Rather a superexchange type of interaction⁶ may be possible through the

π -electron delocalisation in the $-N=N=N-$ and $-N-C=N-$ bridges. Moreover, since four bridging systems are present around each copper (II) ion, the spins of the metal ion will mutually interact in all these directions making a novel type of exchange interaction in the polymeric molecule. Super-exchange through π -electron delocalisation via a $-N=N-$ bridge has been previously observed in some binuclear nickel (II) complexes with dihydrazinophthalazine and dipyridylpyridazine leading to antiferromagnetism at low temperature^{7,8}.

In studying the electronic spectra of the copper (II) complex, $Cu(PPT)_2$, in benzene, the characteristic band at ~ 600 nm is not found because of its being masked by the strongly intense charge transfer band at 380 nm. In its reflectance spectra, however, a broad unsymmetrical band above 600 nm has been observed which may be resolved into two components at 620 and 685 nm suggesting a tetragonal distortion of the complex (Table 2).

Nickel (II) and cobalt (II) have combined with the ligand to form 1 : 2 complexes and from the magnetic moments of 3.26 and 5.37 B.M., respectively, both the complexes appear to be octahedral. Unlike the diphenyltriazenocomplexes¹, no pyridine could be coordinated in these complexes which, like $Cu(PPT)_2$, crystallised unchanged from this highly ligating solvent and may have similar structure as that of the copper (II) complex except that no exchange interaction is present in them at room temperature.

The nickel (II) compound shows an absorption maximum at 1080 nm and a shoulder at 670 nm with molar absorbances of 10.6 and 14.2 respectively. The high energy band around 400 nm has been completely hidden by the intense charge transfer band at 390 nm. The octahedral configuration of cobalt (II) compound is evident from its spectral band at 1060 nm with a low extinction value of 5.4. The other band at ~ 560 nm has been masked by the charge transfer band at 395 nm (Table 2).

In order to establish the identity of stereochemical dispositions of the copper (II), nickel (II) and cobalt (II)

complexes, their x-ray powder diffraction patterns have been taken. The 'd' values and the visual intensities are found to be identical. This proves the isomorphous nature of the crystals and the octahedral configuration of the three complexes (Table 3). The IR spectra of these three complexes also show identical bands in the range $4000-650$ cm^{-1} .

The diamagnetic square planar palladium (II) complexes, $Pd(PPT)X$, where $X=Cl, Br$ or I , are isolated from their respective palladium (II) halides and the ligand. From the molecular model of $Pd(PPT)Cl$, structure like monomeric (Fig. 2) or dimeric (Fig. 3) with pyridine replaced by chlorine, seems to be highly strained due to distortion from natural bond angles. The presence of $Pd-Cl$ stretch⁹ at 362 cm^{-1} in the far IR region excludes the possibility of a bridging chlorine atom in the dimeric structure. A different type of polymeric structure free from any strain and similar to that of Fig. 4 is, therefore, suggested for the

TABLE 3—X-RAY POWDER DIFFRACTION PATTERNS OF COPPER(II) NICKEL (II) AND COBALT(II) COMPLEXES

$Cu(PPT)_2$		$Ni(PPT)_2$		$Co(PPT)_2$	
dÅ	I/I'	dÅ	I/I'	dÅ	I/I'
8.38	9	8.38	10	8.46	9
6.00	w	5.99	w	6.00	w
5.26	3	5.27	3	5.27	4
4.49	1	4.50	1	4.50	1
4.30	2	4.28	2	4.31	2
4.02	w	4.02	w	4.03	w
3.83	10	3.83	9	3.86	10
3.56	w	3.56	w	3.56	w
2.72	5	2.73	4	2.74	3
2.55	w	2.56	w	2.55	w
2.39	1	2.39	1	2.41	1
2.15	1	2.15	1	2.14	1
2.10	1	2.10	1	2.10	1
2.01	6	2.01	5	2.01	5
1.96	6	1.96	5	1.96	5
1.75	2	1.75	2	1.74	2

complex, where the triazene acts as a tridentate ligand forming a 6-membered chelate with chlorine atom in the terminal position. The corresponding bromo and iodo derivatives are supposed to have identical configurations.

The molecular weights of the complexes could not be determined because of their low solubility in any of the solvents.

In the absence of any X-ray structural analysis, no definite conclusion can be drawn as to the configuration of the ligand in the complexes. But it is quite likely that the ligand avoids any configuration which involves 4-membered ring system and preferentially forms 6-membered bridged chelates.

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